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ADAPTATION OF CONVERTING INDUSTRIAL FACILITIES INTO PUBLIC FUNCTIONAL BUILDINGS

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In recent years, the problem of revitalization of industrial areas in the structure of the developing modern city is particularly urgent. The term renovation refers to the flexible use of buildings, structures, complexes when changing their functional purpose.

Key words: renovation, Industrial areas, renovation, reconstruction, restoration

ISHLAB CHIQRARISH OBYEKTLARINI JAMOAT FUNKSIYALI BINOLARIGA AYLANTIRISH ADABTATSIYASIYASI

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So'nggi yillarda rivojlanayotgan zamonaviy shahar tarkibida sanoat hududlarini qayta tiklash muammosi ayniqsa dolzarbdir. Renovatsiya atamasi binolar, inshootlar, komplekslarning funktsional maqsadlarini o'zgartirganda moslashuvchan ishlatilishini anglatadi.

Kalit so'zlar: renovatsiya, Sanoat hududlari, renovatsiya qilish, qayta qurish, qayta tiklash

Introduction In the structure of a developing modern city in recent years, the problem of renovation of industrial areas is particularly relevant. The term renovation refers to the adaptive use of buildings, structures, complexes when their functional purpose changes.

The expediency of renovation, the introduction of alternative functions is determined by social, economic, psychological, historical and aesthetic factors. Many industrial enterprises are transferred from the city center to its outskirts, to the region. If the industrial use of the territory is abandoned, it is envisaged to reduce the negative impact on the environment.

The use of internal territories, the architectural, spatial and functional organization of which today does not correspond to their urban significance and potential, usually does not imply renovation and restoration of enterprises. Therefore, one of the options for using the territory is the

complete demolition of the existing facility and the construction of a new complex from scratch. (Quarter Helisen Kirchen, Germany, architect M. Kowalski - on the territory of the plant for the production of furnaces) [App. 1].

But with this method, the costs for the demolition of objects, for clearing the territory, and so on, increase significantly. Moreover, in many cases, industrial buildings are architectural monuments and are protected by the state (which is very typical for our city [for St. Petersburg - ed.]).

That is why in this work I want to consider examples of various options for the transformation of industrial territories and objects with the preservation of buildings and a change in function, to analyze the experience of various countries and architectural workshops.

Center for Arts and Media Technology in Karlsruhe

I would like to start the comparison with examples from foreign design practice.

The first site I would like to consider is the Center for Arts and Media Technology in Karlsruhe (Zentrum für Kunst und Medientechnologie Karlsruhe), Germany [App. 2].

The placement in 1997 on the territory and in the buildings of the industrial enterprise "IKWA-Karlsruhe-Augsburg" of a modern public center was one of the examples of a radical revision of the role of an industrial facility in the renewal of the urban landscape. The wide, three-story high blocks of the factory building are symmetrically arranged around ten courtyards. The building is made of concrete frames filled with brickwork on the facades. Abandoned in the seventies and then occupied by artists, the building was eventually transferred to a number of industrial architectural monuments.

The competition for the reconstruction, maintenance and expansion of the factory building was won by the architectural firm ASP SCHWEGER ASSOZIIERTE. The architects successfully preserved the 1918 building and introduced new high-tech elements. For example, to avoid the negative impact of noise and vibration on the building, the sound studio was moved outside the factory in the form of a large glass cube in front of the facade.

Modern electronic technology usually requires space - no more than an ordinary box, so in industrial scale halls, with large spans, the factory represented a potentially ideal container.

By blocking the courtyards with lanterns and transforming the interior spaces, the architects have achieved an ideal modern and functional space. Solar generators placed on the roofs feed the tram tracks of the surrounding areas.

Particular attention in this project was given to the transformation of the area around the building, an attempt to create the most natural natural complex around the building, thereby playing with the contrasts between

high technology and a return to nature when leaving the building. The problem with parking was solved by the installation of underground parking throughout the building. The entire area above this garage is a green lawn, with eight modules of artificial relief with tree plantings. The modules are made of metal sheets, thus preserving the "memory of the place", its industrial past.

water museum

In my opinion, one of the successful objects of the reconstruction of an industrial facility, completed by our architects, is the water museum on the territory of the Vodokanal enterprise [App. 7].

The reconstruction of the water tower building is the first experience in St. Petersburg in the revival of old industrial buildings that have lost their former purpose. This project is an experiment in mixing styles of the 19th and 21st centuries. The main task was to restore, cleanse from the later "layers" and adapt the internal spaces of the tower to new functions. Preservation of the integrity of the interiors - beautiful halls with arched ceilings.

"But the way in which we ensured this "conservation" belongs to a completely different architectural strategy. It is rather a sign, a functional sculpture. Not just a strong form - a meaningful form. The architectural essence of any tower is an upward striving, and the glass vertical of the staircase reveals this movement, which is usually hidden from the viewer's eyes. The brick building seems to be duplicated, while losing its materiality," says Evgeny Podgornov, head of the Intercolumnium workshop.

The red-brick octahedron of the water tower, designed by the architects Merze and Shubersky in 1860-1863, is connected with water only functionally: the monolithic volume denies any fluidity. The architects of the Intercolumnium studio, reconstructing the tower, managed to solve not only substantive issues - the placement of the World of Water

Museum in the Tower, but also figurative ones. Requirements for the preservation of the historic interiors of the Tower led to the removal of the elevator and stairs to a separate extension. It was she who became the main focus of the reconstruction. In its forms and material one can read the image of water. Together with the tower, the area around the museum was also successfully transformed. A square was laid out, a fountain was built, and sculptures were put up.

Figure 1

golden island

Now let's turn to projects that have not yet been implemented, let's see what awaits us in the near future.

In Moscow, the discussion of the Golden Island project is in full swing [App. 9].

The Golden Island program covers the territory of the island opposite the Kremlin from the Bolshoy Moskvoretsky Bridge to the monument to Peter the Great on the Spit of the Island and for the first time creates conditions for the integrated development of the territory of the historical center with an area of more

than 40 hectares. We are interested in the part of the island now occupied by the Krasny Oktyabr factory - the western tip of the island.

The factory buildings, which are monuments of industrial architecture, are planned to be reconstructed after its withdrawal. Taking into account the height of the premises and the architecture of the buildings, it is planned to place various public functions and individual "lofts" here - places of residence and work of artists, sculptors and representatives of other creative professions.

On the site of the demolished buildings of the factory, which are not of architectural value, it is planned to erect an elite residential complex. On the western part of the Spit of the Island, in a place surrounded by water on three sides and remote from city highways, there will be a hotel, cafes and restaurants.

This territory, due to its geographical location, is in itself a very attractive recreational and walking area. All the embankments in this area are being transformed into a landscaped walking area designed for free visits by Muscovites and guests of the capital. The western part of the Strelka will be connected by pedestrian bridges to the site of the monument to Peter I and the Park of Arts.

The problem of parking has also been successfully solved in this place. A two-story underground car park with an area of about 50,000 sq.m. will be located under the bottom of the hydraulic structure of the Vodootvodny canal between the monument to Peter I and the Small Stone Bridge. The underground space of the parking lot will be connected to the underground part of the Megapolis Center complex on the Spit of the Island.

Red proletarian

And finally, let's consider an unrealized project, an architectural and planning concept for the development and restructuring of the territory of the Krasny Proletarian plant,

proposed by the famous Moscow architect Sergei Skuratov [App. 10].

In the planning structure of the projected area, the main one is the interpenetration of two urban planning directions: "white" and "red". Their interaction, based on the color scheme of the red-brick and white-stone architecture of the monastery, becomes the main style-forming theme of the new quarter. At the same time, the red color is the monastic and red-brick industrial buildings. The white color of the decorative finish of the monuments of classical Moscow architecture and the main color of the new, light and dynamic architecture of the 20th century. Such a figurative solution allows you to simultaneously preserve the "genius of the place" and rehabilitate it for a new life and new functions.

combined with transport access to houses. Ten courtyard spaces, raised 4 meters above the ground, unite all residential buildings. Each group has a different number of houses, a different configuration in plan and a different functional saturation. Large-sized trees are planted in the central zone of all yard spaces. The perimeter of the yards has different geometry and different solutions.

Under the pedestrian and transport zones-boulevards, underground parking lots with car washes, parking spaces for residents at the rate of two cars per apartment, guest parking spaces and places for employees are organized. At the crossroads of two pedestrian zones, a European-scale square was organized with a hotel building and a shopping and entertainment center for residents of the area located on it.

It is proposed to place an exhibition and educational center with art galleries, an art school and art salons in the preserved and reconstructed factory building along Maly Kaluzhsky Lane.

The peculiarity of the resulting quarter is the absence of a fence and "permeability" - the ability to cross it up and down, for which the coordinating authorities have been fighting for recent years and which Muscovites dream of, remembering the past. It can be said that in the concept of Sergei Skuratov, the option of creating an open city through the vertical separation of public and private space is successfully proposed.

Figure 2

The entire territory of the quarter is divided according to the principle of "private - public" into two categories of spaces. The first category of spaces is pedestrian boulevards

Приложение 10

Conclusion

Thus, using examples from domestic and foreign practices of architectural design and urban planning, we considered various options and methods for introducing new architecture into existing historical industrial buildings. There are quite a few different approaches, and many of them are successful and justified.

The policy of renovation of industrial areas is especially relevant for our city [for St. Petersburg - approx. ed.]. Petersburg may lose the unique monuments of industrial architecture if the city authorities do not take decisive measures to restore them. Many buildings of factories and plants, built in the past centuries, today are in an extremely neglected state, while remaining architectural monuments.

It is not possible today to return all monuments to their original form without investment funds, which is why the city has high hopes for tenants and owners of historical buildings. The policy of creating something new, rethinking industrial buildings, will lead

to an influx of funds, investors, make it possible to recreate and maintain monuments.

The complexes of plants and factories built in St. Petersburg in the 18th - early 20th centuries were originally designed as objects that form a huge industrial space of the city. These are whole ensembles, the architecture of which is not inferior to other monuments of history and culture in terms of its expressiveness and beauty.

The experience of foreign workshops, as well as the successful projects of our architects, is very important. There are many abandoned industrial buildings in the city, for example, on the Obvodny Canal embankment. In our city, new architecture is always a compromise, so the widely practiced practice in the West of combining the language of the classics with the language of the latest architecture is seen as a radical gesture. Therefore, in order to be embodied, he must be deeply comprehended and motivated.

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